

“COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN ONLINE AND OFFLINE PURCHASE OF CONSUMER”

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ABSTRACT

The online is the most promoting concept on trending in India now a day as everyone is looking for the products online and comparing it to the offline. As online is quicker, easier, & time saver shopping? Now a day the internet holds the eye of the retail market place. As now most of the public is being online & the usage on internet has risen in last 5 years. On the other hand, the purchasing of the product from the conventional market is going on. Many people cross for buying offline to have a look at the product & hold the ownership of the product for the result of customer loyalty. Some go for the offline shopping & some go for online, but most of the people go for the both kind of shopping in India. However it had been seen that the online buying is less complicated for the public and less price than the offline purchasing. It is seen that the online shopping is most reliable and saving time it is also shown that in metro city's the online shopping is been boomed in shorter time and being profitable to both the customer and the buyer

Keywords: Online shopping, showroom purchases, offline shopping, methods of payment.

INTRODUCTION

It is seen that the online shopping is likely to be risk the traditional shopping as the trust matter differs. The convenience matter also differs as the people have a different point of view. Sometime the pricing also effects as the price in the online is less compered to offline shopping. Tentative and descriptive research can provide the multiple outlooks necessary to obtain multiple approvals of online, offline and channel switching behavior during the buying decision process. This typically involves sampling the population, surveying them and using inferential statistics to analyze the responses. The focus of the analysis is to expect the determining factors influencing, in this case, what and why consumers purchase online and offline as well, why they switch from one way to another. The data gathered during the depth interviews were used to identify common questions concerning consumer behavior as it relates to the pure online and offline buying process as well as channel switching from one trade channel to another during the buying choice process. Deepness of the interviews and concentration groups provide an efficient means of spreading and emerging theoretical concepts to improve the ultimate research design. And are used in this research to better appreciate what and why consumers use the Internet to shop and in specific why they choose one channel over another in general. Below defines how this qualitative phase of the research is directed and classifies which of the research objectives each activity supports for both the depth interviews.

Factors Affecting Online Shopping

- Risk
- Convenience
- Pricing policy
- Previous online experience
- Quality
- Delivery time
- Offers
- Income

Factors Affecting Offline Shopping

- Less number of choices
- Time consuming
- Bargaining
- Taste and preference

Research

According to Robert Ross, “Research is essentially an investigation, a recording and analysis of evidence for the purpose of gaining knowledge. The goal of research is to discover new facts, establishment of new relationship, creation of new concepts, and verification of existing concepts, finding a solution to a problem or satisfying one’s desire to know.

Research design

Research Design is the conceptual structure with in which research is conducted. It constitutes the blueprint for the collection of measurement and analysis of data. It is the method of finding solution to a problem and adding a new knowledge to the existing body of knowledge.

Objectives of the study

To obtain familiarity of the study.

- To determine the characteristics of sample taken from the whole population.
- To establish new research to contribute to program planning and evolution.

Scope of the study

- To analyze whether online shopping is more convenient way of shopping or mall shopping is considered convenient.
- The study would be based upon the primary data that will be collected through the means of questionnaire by the direct approach.

Research Methodology

Research methodology explains the overarching theoretical and philosophical frameworks which guide the researcher. It aims at the employment of the correct procedures to find out solutions.

Sampling

- It is the subject on which measurement is taken from the whole population. It is the unit of study. A part of the population is known as sample. The process of drawing a sample from the larger population is called as sampling.

Type of Research

It is a comparative research. It is require to find out the difference between the online shopping and offline shopping.

Data Collection

Data collection is of two types. They are:

- Primary data collection: the data collected by observation, personal interview, telephone interview, by mailing questionnaires and survey.
- Secondary data collection: The data collected by obtaining from existing records, publications, journals, magazines, etc.

PROCESS OF ONLINE SHOPPING

A consumer uses web browser to connect to the home page of a merchant's web site on the internet.

PAYMENT GATEWAY

METHODS OF PAYMENT

Online shoppers commonly use a credit card or a PayPal account in order to make payments. However, some systems enable users to create accounts and pay by alternative means, such as

- Credit card
- Debit card
- Payment websites
- PayPal
- Wire Transfer
- Electronic money of various types
- Purchase order
- Checks and Money order
- Mobile Payments
- Bank Transfer
- Cash On Delivery (COD)

Some online shops will not accept international credit cards. Some require both the purchaser's billing and shipping address to be in the same country as the online shop's base of operation. Other online shops allow customers from any country to send gifts anywhere. The financial part of a transaction may be processed in real time (e.g. letting the consumer know their credit card was declined before they log off), or may be done later as part of the fulfilment process.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Research dealing with shopping malls' and / or hypermarkets' attributes, especially in the Indian context, is very less in number. Not many studies have empirically analyzed the influence of an assortment of attributes on buying behavior in shopping arcades and malls and

customers' shopping experiences. Mostly the researches undertaken so far have been taken from the foreign experiences, as they have come of age in the US, UK and European markets. An earnest attempt has been made to delve into the relevant researches done on the theme, presented henceforth as follows:

Brunner and Mason (1968) investigated the importance of driving time upon the preferences of consumers towards regional shopping centers. They expressed that although it is recognized that population, purchasing power, population density, newspaper circulation, and other factors are influential in determining the shopping habits of consumers, a factor which is generally overlooked is the driving time required to reach the center. In this study, it was established that the driving time required to reach a center is highly influential in determining consumer shopping Center preferences. The most consistent and significant driving time dimension in Delineating shopping center trade areas was found at the 15-minute driving points, as Three-fourths of each center's shoppers resided within this range.

Huff (1964 and 1966) concluded that the comparative size of the centers and the convenience of access were the primary characteristics that consumers sought when choosing a shopping center to visit.

Jackson, Stole and Brantley (2011) in their paper expressed that the customer segments seek out relevant shopping venues based on their shopping wants and needs. Knowledge of the preferences of distinct consumer groups is useful in the development of marketing communications and promotional strategies, as well as for designing mall configurations that are likely to generate patronage and repatronage due to the value creating potential of the mall. Advertising materials could express the specific attributes the mall has to offer to the cohorts comprising its customer base, either by gender, generation, or both. When a retailer or mall owner finds that a large segment of its consumers are from particular segments (e.g. generation, gender), the company can focus on segment relevant ways to facilitate and promote a shopping experience that will drive shopping value and create potential for repatronage. Consumer behavior has changed greatly over the past decades, but it has been evolutionary and the seeds of change have been apparent for generations (**K r, 2010**). **Pi ush K. Sinh ,Arind m B nerjee, ndDwrikPr s d Uni l,(2002)**, identified major drivers behind choice of stores for various shopping needs as exhibited by a typical Indian consumer, by conducting study on 293 participates recruited by e-mail.

Ton Ahn, Seewon R u ndIngoo H n, (2015), explored online and offline features of Internet shopping malls and their relationships with the acceptance behaviors of customers. Web survey with 932 users was conducted in 6 shopping malls of korea. The study validate technology acceptance model (TAM) in predicting the acceptance of the Internet shopping malls. Online and offline features have positive effects on the user acceptance, usefulness, attitude and intention to use.

Aron M. Levin, Irwin P. Levin nd Joshu A. Weller,(2010), For the study two samples of size 199 were used from a large mid-western American university and an online survey panel. The study found that the preferences for shopping online or offline were shown to vary across

products, consumers, and stages of the shopping experience. When attributes such as large selection and shopping quickly were predominant, online shopping was preferred. When attributes such as personal service and ability to see-touch-handle the product were predominant, offline shopping was preferred.

Junhong Chu et. l. (2010), explored the moderating effects of household (e.g., shopping frequency) and product (e.g., sensory nature) characteristics on brand loyalty, size loyalty and price sensitivity across online and offline channels for grocery products. Data was collected from one of the five leading grocery chains in Spain. The study of found that the households were more brand loyal and size loyal but less price sensitive in the online channel than in the offline channel.

Rick L. Andrews Ourso ndImr n S. Currim, examined behavioral differences between consumers attracted to online shopping and traditional supermarket shopping using actual choice data from an online supermarket and traditional scanner panel data. The study found that as Compared to traditional supermarket consumers, online consumers prefer larger sizes to smaller sizes, do more screening on the basis of brand names, do less screening on the basis of sizes, have stronger choice set effects.

Koen P uwels et. l., (2011), found that the offline revenue impact of the informational website critically depends on the product category and customer segment. The lower online search costs were especially beneficial for sensory products and for customers distant from the store. In contrast, customers in a particular segment reduce their shopping trips, suggesting their online actions partially substitute for experiential shopping in the physical store.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

1. Age groups of samplings.

Particular	Percent
Below 20	35%
20-30	35%
30-40	26%
40-50	4%

Interpretation:-

The above graph tells the Age group of samplings that have been collected during the survey.

2. Division of gender in samplings.

Particular	Percent
Male	54%
Female	36%

Interpretation-;

The above chart is shown the number of male samplings i.e. 62% and rest 38% are female samplings

3. Type of shopping preferred

Particular	Percent
Online Shopping	58%
Retail Marketing	42%

Interpretation:-

The above graph shows what shopping methods do people prefer between online shopping and retail or mall shopping, there are some people who prefer both the method. The data is based upon the survey which I took thorough questioner in Orion mall. 58% of people like online shopping and 42% of people like offline.

4. Frequency of visiting shopping malls

Particular	Percent
Very Often	35%
Often	35%
Rarely	26%
No	4%

Interpretation-:

The above pie chart shows how often people like to visit malls. As green and blue color shows 35% of people like to go very often and rarely, and 35 % of people like to go often where as no one like not to visit malls.

5. Opinion regarding Usage of online shopping

Particular	Percent
Yes	73%
NO	27%

Interpretation-:

This chart shows the percentage of people who had made online shopping. In the pie chart we can see 73% of people had mad online shopping where as 27% of people didn't. These 27% of people are shown as nil if further online shopping related question.

6. People usually like to visit shopping mall on.

Particular	Percent
Weeks Days	19%
Weekends	35%
Holidays	36%
Occasionally	10%

Interpretation:-

This chart shows when people like most to visit malls. The percentage of people visit to mall is higher in holidays by 36% whereas 45% people like to go occasionally and on weekends. Remaining 19% like to visit on weeks days.

7. People thinking about advertisements as good source of information regarding shopping malls

Particular	Percent
Yes	64%
No	36%

Interpretation:-

This graph shows people thinking about advertisements as good source of information regarding shopping malls. 64% of people are agree with the sentence where as 36%are won't.

8. People mostly like to visit online shopping on

Particular	Percent
Weekly	20%
Monthly	42%
Occasionally	26%
None	12%

Interpretation:-

This chart shows when people like most to visit online shopping. The percentage of people visit to mall is higher on monthly bases 42% whereas 26% people like to shop occasionally and 20% on weekly bases. Remaining 12% of them don't shop online.

9. The expenditure of individual per month in shopping mall.

Particular	Percent
100-500	24%
500-1000	22%
1001-2000	40%
5000	14.0%

Interpretation:-

The above chart tells the expenditure of individual per month in shopping mall 24% of them spend 100-500, 22% of sampling spend 500-1000, major i.e. 40% of samples spend 1001-2000 and 14% of samples spend 5000.

10. Ratings given by sampling to the employee behavior in shopping malls out of 5

Particular	Percent
1	2%
2	10%
3	28%
4	34%
5	26%

Interpretation:-

When it comes to employee rating at mall, 40% of people had rate them the highest 3 where as 25% of people had rate them 4 and 15% of people had given 5. We can also see the 5% people had rated 1 and 15% had rated 2.

Rate of experience give on shopping online out of 5.

Particular	Percent
1	8%
2	6%
3	18%
4	36%
5	32%

Interpretation:-

When it's come to rating for online shopping experience , 36% of people had rate them the highest is **4**, where as 32% of people had rate 5 and 18% of people had given 3. We can also see the 8% people had rated 1 and 6% had rated 2.

11. Availability of new style and designs in

Particular	Percent
Shopping mall	30%
Online shopping	66%
Street shopping	4%

Interpretation:-

The above pie chart show the people believe about the product of new style and designs and there availability at online shopping. As we can see 66% people thought online shopping and 30% Retail shopping.

12. Percentage of people shopping daily use products from shopping malls

Particular	Percent
Yes	30%
No	70%

Interpretation:-

Above chart shows that 70% of people don't purchase daily use product from mall where as 30% do.

People perception on difference between shopping mall & general store

Particular	Percent
Yes	80%
NO	20%

Interpretation:-

In the above pie chart it is shown that what people really think about the difference between shopping malls and general store. 80% of people believe yes there is a difference where as 20% of people doesn't think so.

13. Consumers perception on quality of product are available in malls

Particular	Percent
Yes	40%
NO	60%

Interpretation:-

In the above pie chart it is shown that what people really think about the high price and good quality product availability in malls and other shop. 60% of people believe yes where as 40% of people don't think so.

14. Expenditure on online shopping per month

Particular	Percent
100-500	24%
500-1000	22%
1001-2000	29%
5000	25%

Interpretation:-

The above chart tells the expenditure of individual per month in shopping mall 24% of them spend 100-500, 22% of sampling spend 500-1000, major i.e. 29% of samples spend 1001-2000 and 25% of samples spend 5000.

15. People recommend others to use online shopping.

Particular	Percent
Yes	85%
NO	15%

Interpretation:-

Above chart shows that 85% of people recommend others to use online shopping where as 15% doesn't support for online shopping.

16. Which mall do you prefer the most for shopping?

Particular	Percent
Orion	40%
Mantri	28%
Garuda	10%
Forum	15%
Other	7%

Interpretation-:

Above chart shows that 40% of people visit Orion mall, 28% of them go to Mantri mall , 10% of them go to Garuda mall , and rest of them i.e. 7% of them visit other malls

Findings on online shopping

Among the top findings of the survey, as put forth by Online Shopping, are the following:

- ❖ Convenience was listed as the top reason for shopping online by 74% of the respondents, and at the same level were purchase goods in online. This is good news for e-tailers, as the value proposition for online shopping is clear in the minds of shoppers.
- ❖ 27% of our respondents said they aren't purchase of their goods online. We believe this bodes well for e-tailers as online shopping is gaining acceptance.
- ❖ 95% of respondents look for products information and service information before purchasing.

Conclusion on online shopping

- ❖ After having detail study on Online Shopping one can see a great change in the behaviour of people in many manners like their attitude, buying pattern. In earlier times people use to do manual shopping but now as time changed people are becoming busy and due to which technology has brought a new revolution i.e. Online Shopping.
- ❖ As we started doing survey it came to in notice that young age group people i.e. 15-30 uses or prefer online shopping because it is time and energy saving. But middle-age group does not prefer much because they have wrong perception that by seeing the product one can get the goods of proper quality. And even some people does not prefer using plastic money i.e. credit cards.
- ❖ In 95% of the purchases, the terms and conditions were available before entering into a purchase process, but the legal requirement to inform about the cooling-off period was only met in 82% of the purchases. This means that in 18% of the purchases, the Mystery Shopper was not informed about the legal right to withdraw from the contract. This is a rather disturbing result. However, it was worse to discover that the websites contained information about the legal warranty and the rights connected to it in only 37% of the purchases. Furthermore the information given about these rights was only correct in 80% of the cases.
- ❖ In only 68% of the purchases did the trader provide information to consumers on the process of completing the purchase? The figure is higher when it comes to providing the consumers with the possibility to review the details of the order before placing it. This possibility was provided for in 89% of the purchases. The obligation to provide this information follows from the E-commerce Directive.

Findings on shopping mall

- ❖ 45% of respondents look for not to waste of their time.
- ❖ Reason for shopping mall by 44% of the respondents, and at the same level was purchase goods in online. This is good news for e-tailers, as the value proposition for online shopping is clear in the minds of shoppers.
- ❖ 56% of our respondents said they were purchase of their goods in shopping malls. We believe this bodes well for as shopping is gaining acceptance.
- ❖ 55% of respondents look for product checking and service information before purchasing.

Conclusion on shopping mall

- ❖ The share of modern retail market in India was around 5% in 2008 is very low compared to countries in the west, where the share of modern retail to the total retail is 75-80 percent. Therefore there is tremendous potential for the modern retail formats like malls to grow in India. Mall boom in India started in 2003 and continues to thrive after a setback in 2008-09 because of recession. There are malls which are doing well including those established in the formative years like Ansal Plaza, Delhi. However malls which jumped into the fray without any planning and strategy are having troubles with low footfalls and low retailer occupancy. This research was conducted with the intention to help developers in a capital intensive sector to avoid the mistakes of the past and benefit from being a part of the booming retail sector.
- ❖ One of the important conclusions is that there is a lack of clarity amongst mall developers regarding positioning and image. As shown in the table 8, the focus is on image which is a combination of functional and psychological attributes of the mall [117]. Hence there is an attempt to provide aesthetic design, range of retail outlets, good ambience, good security and so on. All these are important functions of mall development and mall management. However apart from focussing on the above, there is no effort to develop a positioning strategy which is critical for the success of a mall. Without a positioning strategy, all the malls are similar to each other. Hence, it can be reasoned that, such lack of differentiation is the reason behind increasing retailer vacancy levels and reduced shopper footfall.

Positioning constructs, convenience, shopping experience, entertainment, property management and ambience has a positive influence on shopper satisfaction. Convenience has the highest impact on the mall, followed by shopping experience. The least positive influence is caused by the positioning construct ambience, perhaps because it is taken for granted as all the malls are able to provide good ambience. It could not be proved in the study that promotions positively influence shopper satisfaction.

Recommendation on online shopping

- ❖ They should provide complete information about their products and should make site simple so that common people can understand how to make purchase - As in online one purchase goods through credit cards but one can use the approach of cash payment during delivery - One can use more animation through which they can attract more customers - One can use the approach of credit points i.e. if one purchase for the first time they get credit points due to which if they purchase for the second time they can get discount of that much points. Due to which one increase the repurchase.

Suggestions on online shopping

- ❖ Security for consumer's personal details.
- ❖ More details about the latest products and service information
- ❖ Web site design can easy to understand for consumer.
- ❖ No minimum purchase for free Shipping.
- ❖ Decrease the shipping misplacement.
- ❖ More offers for consumers.
- ❖ Delivery of goods has to deliver within 36 hours.

Recommendation on shopping mall

- ❖ One can use more animation through which they can attract more customers.
- ❖ They should provide complete information about their products and should make mall simple so that common people can understand how to make purchase.
- ❖ As in shopping mall purchase of goods through credit cards but one can use the approach of cash payment during delivery
- ❖ One can use the approach of credit points i.e. if one purchase for the first time they get credit points due to which if they purchase for the second time they can get discount of that much points. Due to which one increase the repurchase.

Suggestions on shopping mall

- ❖ More products and services information for consumers.
- ❖ Free parking for consumers vehicles.
- ❖ Events for festivals.
- ❖ Proper emergency exit for people.
- ❖ Lotteries for who comes to shopping mall regularly.

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